

Extended Theoretical Investigations Based on The Best Light-Emitting Electrochemical Cell (LEEC) Champions Reported in Early 2022

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The emission spectra and phosphorescence quantum yield of top-performing iridium (III) complexes, each containing distinct cyclometallated ligands, were analyzed using density functional theory (DFT) and time-dependent DFT (TD-DFT) approaches. The computed photophysical properties of these iridium complexes aligned well with the experimental data. All complexes show emissions characterized as a mixture of triplet ligand-to-ligand charge transfer (³LLCT) and metal-to-ligand charge transfer (³MLCT) states. The vertical emission energies calculated at the B3LYP level for the 1–4 complexes are located at 2.7, 2.4, 2.1, and 2.9 eV, respectively. Based on these results, theoretical calculations can provide accurate predictions of the electronic and photophysical properties of iridium complexes and then can be used to guide the synthesis of new phosphorescent materials.

1. Introduction

Iridium-based ionic transition metal complexes (Ir-iTMCs) have gained prominence as emitters in light-emitting electrochemical cells (LEECs), offering a simpler device structure, lower production costs, and good solution processability compared to traditional organic light-emitting diodes (OLEDs) [1, 2]. The frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) of these complexes have been identified using density functional theory (DFT) methods [1-5]. By modifying the cyclometallated and/or ancillary ligands, the bandgap can be adjusted to emit light across the visible spectrum [1, 6]. Previously, literature highlighted that incorporating five-membered nitrogen-rich heterocycles with peripheral phenyl groups into cyclometallated ligands yields highly efficient light-emitting electrochemical cells (LEECs), often recognized as champion devices [1, 2]. The peripheral phenyl groups enhance efficiency by introducing steric hindrance; this increases inter-complex distances and effectively suppresses nonradiative decay in the solid state [1, 2]. While earlier computational studies using density functional theory (DFT) and time-dependent DFT (TD-DFT) evaluated a series of highly efficient iridium complexes featuring 2,2'-bipyridine (bpy) ancillary ligands and phenyltriazole-type cyclometallated ligands [1-3], the present study theoretically investigates a second class of efficient champion iridium complexes with alternative

cyclometallated and ancillary ligand configurations. [3]. The calculated photophysical results correlate with experimental data, offering clear molecular design principles for engineering novel emissive materials (Figure 1.).

Figure 1. Chemical structures of the champion iridium complexes.

2. Computational details

Gaussian09 was used to optimize the ground and excited states of the compounds using DFT [8]. The restricted Becke, 3-parameter, Lee-Yang-Parr

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(B3LYP) model was used for ground-state optimization, while the unrestricted B3LYP method was applied to optimize the triplet states [9-11]. Vibrational frequencies were calculated to confirm that the optimized structures represent local minima. The compounds were optimized in toluene and acetonitrile using the polarizable continuum model, which accounts for electrostatic interactions with the solvent. Based on the optimized ground-state geometries, electronic transitions were calculated via TD-DFT, determining the energy and oscillator strength for the 25 lowest-energy singlet-singlet transitions. Additionally, the energies of the emissive states were obtained via TD-DFT by calculating the energy and oscillator strength for the 10 lowest-energy triplet molecular orbitals [9,12]. The calculated energy gaps and frontier molecular orbitals (FMOs) were visualized using Chemissian software.

3. Results and Discussion

The chemical structures of the iridium complexes studied are displayed in Figure S1 of the Electronic Supporting Information (ESI). "All of the iridium complexes exhibit a pseudo-octahedral geometry around the Iridium center, similar to most reported Ir complexes" [1-3, 7]. To better understand the structural variations between the ground state (S_0) and the first triplet excited state (T_1), key geometric parameters for these states are presented in (Table S2, ESI). According to recent research, the B3LYP functional has proven to provide reliable and generally accurate geometries for calculating the lowest energy emissions [1].

The transition characteristics of the complexes were consistent, involving a mix of 3MLCT (metal-to-ligand charge transfer) and 3LLCT (ligand-to-ligand charge transfer) transitions [3, 4, 8, 9]. The calculated T_1 states were found to be 3.5 eV for complex 1, 2.4 eV for complex 2, 2.1 eV for complex 3, and 2.9 eV for complex 4 above the S_0 states. The T_2 states predominantly involved 3LLCT transitions [$\pi C^{\wedge}N \rightarrow \pi^* C^{\wedge}N$] and were located 0.3–1.2 eV above the T_1 states (vertical energy). Significant energy differences between the T_1 and T_2 states in complexes 1, 3, and 4 indicated that these complexes emitted primarily from the T_1 state [10]. However, complex 2 had a narrow band gap of 0.08 eV, suggesting potential emission from both T_1 and T_2 states.

The percentage of metal character (Mc, %) was used to assess the charge transfer properties (CT) of the complexes [3, 10, 11]. Due to the substantial metal character in iridium complexes, they typically exhibit a high photoluminescence quantum yield (ϕ_{PL}), as described by Equation 1 [8, 10-16]:

$$\phi_{PL} = \frac{k_r}{(k_{nr} + k_r)}, \quad (1)$$

In Equation 1, k_{nr} represents the nonradiative decay constant (s^{-1}) and k_r represents the radiative decay constant (s^{-1}). This equation demonstrates that both k_r and k_{nr} influence the quantum yield, with a low k_n and/or a high k_r leading to a higher ϕ_{PL} . Furthermore, k_r is related to orbital mixing between the T_1 and S_1 states, which is proportional to spin-orbit coupling (SOC) and inversely proportional to the energy gap between T_1 and S_1 ($\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$) [3, 7, 11-14, 17]. For iridium complexes, the relationship between k_r and the metal character has been previously proposed, along with a linear relationship between $\Delta E(T_1 \rightarrow S_0)$ and $\ln(k_{nr})$ [3, 15, 16, 18]. Table 1 lists the calculated values for metal character (%Mc), k_r , k_{nr} , and ϕ_{PL} .

All the complexes show ϕ_{PL} and k_r values consistent with experimental data. A smaller $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$ and a larger %Mc in the emissive states enhance k_r . According to Table 1, the metal character percentages for complexes 1–4 were 30%, 16%, 17%, and 19.0%, respectively, while the $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$ values for complexes 1–4 were 0.20, 0.44, 0.41, and 0.12 eV, respectively. The order of decreasing $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$ was $2 > 3 > 1 > 4$, with the lowest value observed for complex 4 (0.12 eV). The estimated k_r values for the iridium complexes decreased in the order $2 < 3 < 4 < 1$.

During the transition from the S_0 to T_1 states, complex 1 exhibited weak interaction between the Ir atom and the ancillary ligand (phpzpy), as reflected in the elongation of the Ir–N bonds (0.013 and 0.022 Å), which contributed to a low quantum yield of 4% [5]. Despite this, the low $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$ of 0.20 eV, a high dipole moment (μ_{S_1}) of 0.56 Debye, a moderate %Mc of 30.1, and a low k_{nr} of $1.7 \times 10^6 s^{-1}$ suggest other contributing factors. The reduced quantum yield is likely due to π – π stacking interactions, which promote aggregation and self-quenching [1, 2].

Complexes 2 and 3 showed variations in bond lengths, with both elongation and contraction occurring in the Ir–N bonds at the ancillary ligands (dphphen, phpybi). The contraction of Ir–C bonds in the cyclometallated ligands, alongside the elongation of Ir–N bonds, suggests weak interaction between the Ir and ancillary ligands, reflected in %Mc values of 16 for complex 2 and 17 for complex 3, consistent with experimental results [4, 19].

In contrast, complex 4 displayed contracted Ir–N bonds in the ancillary ligand (qibi) (0.118 and 0.001 Å) and elongated Ir–N bonds in the cyclometallated ligands (0.001 and 0.019 Å). The strong interaction between the metal and the qibi ligand in the T_1 state facilitated charge transfer from Ir to the ligand, as expected with a small $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$ of 0.12 eV, a

Table 1. Calculated adiabatic and vertical emission energies (in eV), $k_r/10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{nr}/10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$, quantum yield, and metal character (ϕ_{em} , and $M_c\%$) obtained by B3LYP method, together with the available experimental values.

Complex	E_{0-0}^a	E_v^b	ΔS_1-T_1	K_r	K_{nr}	ϕ_{em}	M_c	$\Delta\mu(S_1-S_0)$ Debye	$E_{Exp.}^c$	K_r	K_{nr}	ϕ_{em}	REF.
1	2.1	2.7	0.20	4.1	1.7	71	30	0.56	2.4	1.4	3.3	04	[4]
1-ppy	2.5	2.8	0.19	4.2	0.01	93	33	0.68	2.6	-	-	3	[20]
2	2.3	2.4	0.44	3.0	0.1	96	16	-0.29*	2.6	-	-	61	[21]
2-ppy	2.1	2.6	0.36	2.9	1.7	63	15	0.31	2.1	-	-	53	[22]
3	2.0	2.1	0.41	3.1	6.0	34	17	-0.92*	2.2	1.0	0.4	19	[5]
3-ppy	2.0	2.4	0.35	2.1	6.0	26	10	-0.71*	2.2	1.5	1.5	09	[23]
4	1.9	2.9	0.12	4.4	21.5	17	19	0.18	1.8	-	-	-	[24]
4-ppy	1.8	2.1	0.27	3.4	76.9	04	19	-0.02*	2.0	0.7	2.1	03	[23]

^a calculated adiabatic emission energy, ^b calculated vertical emission energy using [(TD-KS)^{EES} - (HF)^{EGs}], ^c experimental emission energy measured at RT, * the negative values indicate that the dipole moment in the S_0 states is larger than that of the S_1 states.

moderate μS_1 of 0.18 Debye, an %Mc of 83, and a k_r of $4.4 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

It is possible that the ^3MC state serves as one of the deactivation pathways, occurring alongside phosphorescence emission from the T_1 states. Theoretically, this could be confirmed by observing elongation of the Ir–N bonds in the ancillary ligands (indicating rapid dissociation) and small energy splitting between the d-orbitals. In other words, increasing the energy gap between the non-emissive ^3MC state and the emissive $^3\text{MLCT}/^3\text{LLCT}$ states is an effective strategy to reduce nonradiative transitions. This energy gap was calculated for each of the optimized T_1 states, with the results displayed in Figure 2. All the complexes exhibited ^3MC states at higher energy levels than the $^3\text{MLCT}/^3\text{LLCT}$ states" [3]. However, complex 1 had the smallest energy gap between the $^3\text{MLCT}/^3\text{LLCT}$ and ^3MC states, resulting in a higher likelihood of transition from ^3MC to $^3\text{MLCT}/^3\text{LLCT}$, which accounts for its low quantum yield of 4% [3, 5].

Figure 2. Energy level diagram of emissive ($^3\text{MLCT}/^3\text{LLCT}$) and non-emissive (^3MC) states calculated for the optimized T_1 geometry.

Since these complexes incorporate variable ancillary and cyclometallated ligand frameworks, their photophysical properties can best be evaluated relative to phenylpyridine (ppy) standards. Notably, the theoretical results align well with experimental observations. Attaching a (phpzpy) group to the pyridine ring of the cyclometallated ligand leads to a contraction of the Ir–N bonds (0.0014, 0.0019, 0.0066 Å) and an elongation of the Ir–C bonds (0.0026, 0.0015, 0.0042 Å) in both the ancillary and cyclometallated ligands. This subtle adjustment results in a slight increase in the ^3MC energy (0.02 eV) and a reduction in emission energy (0.38 eV), as noted in the ESI.

Replacing the pyridine group in ppy with a pyrazole moiety (complex 2) increases the emission energy by 1.04 eV, which is consistent with the experimental value of 0.55 eV. Additionally, strong metal–ligand (M–L) interactions, evidenced by the

contraction of the Ir–N bonds (0.0037, 0.0066, 0.0471, 0.0291 Å), are observed in both the ancillary and cyclometallated ligands. This change is associated with an increase in the metal character from 15.4% in 2-ppy to 16.1% in complex 2, along with a rise in the ^3MC energy by 0.11 eV.

Furthermore, replacing the pyridine group with a triazole moiety (complex 3) reduces the emission energy by 0.74 eV, matching experimental results of 0.22 eV. The ^3MC energy increased by 0.20 eV, and the metal character rose by 7%. Additionally, replacing pyridine with a highly conjugated system like N-phenyl benzimidazole (complex 4) significantly boosts the %Mc to 83, enhances the μS_1 to 0.18 Debye, and raises the radiative constant k_r to $4.4 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

4. Conclusion

The photophysical properties of a series of iridium(III) complexes were assessed using time-dependent density functional theory (TD-DFT). All complexes show quantum yield and radiative decay values consistent with experimental data, i.e., a larger %Mc and a smaller $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$, lead to an enhanced k_r . Weak bonding between the iridium atom and the ancillary ligand in complex 1 caused the Ir–N bonds to stretch, leading to a poor quantum yield of only 4%. This low quantum yield is likely driven by intermolecular π – π stacking interactions that induce aggregation-caused quenching. For complexes 2 and 3, structural changes in the Ir–N and Ir–C bonds indicate weak interactions between the iridium core and the ancillary ligands. This weak bonding is supported by low metal character (%Mc) values of 16% and 17%, respectively. On the other hand, complex 4 showed shorter Ir–N bonds in the ancillary ligand and longer Ir–N bonds in the cyclometallated ligands, indicating of a strong interaction between the metal and the ancillary ligand in the T_1 state. As a result, it facilitated charge transfer from Ir to the ligand, affording a moderate k_r , μS_1 , and %Mc associated with a small $\Delta E(S_1-T_1)$. Further work will evaluate the performance of these complexes in OLED/LEEC devices.

Author Contribution

The author confirms sole responsibility for the conception of the study, data collection, analysis, interpretation of results, and manuscript preparation.

Data Availability Statement

The data that supports the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Declaration of Ethical Standards

The author(s) of this article declare that the materials and methods used in this study do not require ethical committee permission and/or legal special permission.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest in this study.

References

- [1] Alsaeedi, M.S., Insight into luminescent iridium complexes: Their potential in light-emitting electrochemical cells. *Journal of Saudi Chemical Society*, **26**(2), 101442, (2022).
- [2] Alsaeedi, M.S., Comprehensive overview into luminescent iridium complexes: best reported light-emitting electrochemical cells up to 2022. *Current Topics and Emerging Issues in Chemical Science*. BP International, (2023).
- [3] Alsaeedi, M.S., A theoretical study on the electronic structures and phosphorescence properties of light-emitting electrochemical cell champions reported in early 2022. *Polyhedron*, **242**, 116490, (2023).
- [4] Meng, X., Chen, M., Bai, R., and He, L., Cationic iridium complexes with 3, 4, 5-triphenyl-4 H-1, 2, 4-triazole type cyclometalating ligands: Synthesis, characterizations, and their use in light-emitting electrochemical cells. *Inorganic Chemistry*, **59**(14), 9605-9617, (2020).
- [5] Song, Y., Ren, H., Meng, X., and He, L., Cationic iridium complexes with an alkyl-linked bulky group at the cyclometalating ligand: synthesis, characterization, and suppression of phosphorescence concentration-quenching. *New Journal of Chemistry*, **45**(34), 15312-15320, (2021).
- [6] Henwood, A.F. and Zysman-Colman, E., A Comprehensive Review of Luminescent Iridium Complexes Used in Light-Emitting Electrochemical Cells (LEECs). *Iridium (III) in Optoelectronic and Photonics Applications*, 275-357, (2017).
- [7] Shang, X., Han, D., Liu, M., and Zhang, G., A theoretical study on the electronic and photophysical properties of two series of iridium (III) complexes with different substituted N[^] N ligand. *RSC advances*, **7**(9), 5055-5062, (2017).
- [8] Wang, X., Wang, S., Pan, F., He, L., and Duan, L., Cationic iridium complexes with 5-phenyl-1 H-1, 2, 4-triazole type cyclometalating ligands: toward blue-shifted emission. *Inorganic Chemistry*, **58**(18), 12132-12145, (2019).
- [9] Yu, R., Song, Y., Chen, M., and He, L., Green to blue-green-emitting cationic iridium complexes with a CF₃-substituted phenyl-triazole type cyclometalating ligand: synthesis, characterization and their use for efficient light-emitting electrochemical cells. *Dalton Transactions*, **50**(23), 8084-8095, (2021).
- [10] Cortés-Arriagada, D., Dreyse, P., Salas, F., and Gonzalez, I., Insights into the luminescent properties of anionic cyclometalated iridium (III) complexes with ligands derived from natural products. *International Journal of Quantum Chemistry*, **118**(17), e25664, (2018).
- [11] Han, D., Gong, P., Lv, S., Zhao, L., and Zhao, H., DFT/TDDFT investigation on the photophysical properties of a series of phosphorescent cyclometalated complexes based on the benchmark complex Flrpic. *Molecular Physics*, **116**(9), 1218-1226, (2018).
- [12] Gao, J., Li, X., Han, D., Li, J., and Shang, X., Theoretical investigation of the electronic structure and photophysical properties of a series of Ir (III) complexes bearing pentafluorosulfanyl groups. *New Journal of Chemistry*, **43**(25), 9916-9923, (2019).
- [13] Han, D., Liu, J., Miao, R., Zhao, L., and Zhang, G., Theoretical design study on the electronic structure and photophysical properties of a series of osmium (II) complexes with different ancillary ligands. *Polyhedron*, **85**, 506-510, (2015).
- [14] Shang, X., Han, D., Zhan, Q., Zhou, D., and Zhang, G., Theoretical investigation of the effects of N-substitution on the photophysical properties of two series of iridium (III) complexes. *New Journal of Chemistry*, **39**(4), 2588-2595, (2015).
- [15] Urinda, S., Das, G., Pramanik, A., and Sarkar, P., Tuning the phosphorescence and quantum efficiency of heteroleptic Ir (III) complexes based on pyridine-tetrazole as an ancillary ligand: An overview from quantum chemical investigations. *Computational and Theoretical Chemistry*, **1092**, 32-40, (2016).
- [16] Urinda, S., Das, G., Pramanik, A., and Sarkar, P., Theoretical studies on the photophysical properties of some Iridium (III) complexes used for OLED. *Journal of Physics and Chemistry of Solids*, **96**, 100-106, (2016).
- [17] Han, D., Zhang, Q., Zhao, L., Zhang, G., and Wang, Q., Theoretical study on the electronic structures and phosphorescent properties of five bis-cyclometalated iridium (III) complexes with 2-phenylpyridinato ancillary ligand. *Synthetic metals*, **191**, 47-52, (2014).
- [18] Wang, L., Wang, N., Zhang, Y., He, H., and Zhang, J., Color tuning from red to green of bis-cyclometalated iridium (III) emitters based on benzoimidazole ligands in OLEDs: A DFT and TD-DFT investigation. *Synthetic metals*, **194**, 160-169, (2014).
- [19] Yi, R.-H., Lo, C.-L., Luo, D., Lin, C.-H., Weng, S.-W., Lu, C.-W., Liu, S.-W., Chang, C.-H., and Su, H.-C., Combinational approach to realize highly efficient light-emitting electrochemical cells. *ACS applied materials & interfaces*, **12**(12), 14254-14264, (2020).